

A Gamified Mobile Framework to Enhance Homework Compliance in Sri Lankan Primary Education

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Abstract

Homework plays a crucial role in reinforcing classroom learning and developing essential skills among primary school students. However, in many Sri Lankan government schools, homework compliance remains low due to limited parental involvement, low student motivation, and inadequate monitoring mechanisms. This study proposes a conceptual framework for a localized and gamified mobile application designed to improve homework compliance in primary education. A systematic literature review was conducted using Google Scholar, focusing on studies related to homework practices, parental engagement, mobile learning, and user-centered educational technologies. Findings indicate that parental participation, contextualized digital tools, and culturally adaptive designs are critical to enhancing student commitment. The proposed mobile framework integrates parental monitoring, teacher feedback, gamified motivation, and offline functionality to address technological and literacy barriers in rural schools. By combining family–school collaboration theories with mobile learning principles, the framework fosters stronger teacher–parent–student connections and continuous feedback loops. This study’s novelty lies in integrating gamified motivation, cultural localization, and policy alignment within a single model to promote sustainable homework engagement. Future work will focus on developing and pilot-testing the proposed application to evaluate its impact on student performance and parental involvement.

Keywords: *Homework Compliance, Mobile Learning, Parental Involvement, Primary Education, Educational Technology.*